

STUDIES ON THE ADSORPTION OF HUMIC ACID ON H-CLAYS AND THE ROLE OF METAL CATIONS IN HUMUS ADSORPTION

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Adsorption of humus by H-clay in different proportions of their mixtures and the role of metal cations in humus adsorption have been studied thoroughly. The results establish two types of linkages between clay and humus—one is a weak bonding where humic acid can be easily extracted by alkali treatment and the other, a strong bonding corresponding to alkali non-extractable portion, where clay, humic acid, and the added cation are involved.

In a previous communication (*Ind. J. Appl. Chem.*, 1960, 23, 145) it has been shown from base-exchange measurements that humic acid and clay minerals do interact leading to a decrease of b.e.c., but the exact nature of this interaction is not clear from this study. In the colloidal state both humic acid and clay are negatively charged. Consequently, mutual coagulation is out of the question. Under the conditions of the experiments an exchange of humate ions for lattice OH does not appear very likely. There is another possibility of a certain kind of co-ordination of the anionic colloidal species with a common cation. This possibility has been studied by determining the adsorption of humic acid by clays in presence of different cations.

Sideri (*Soil Sci.*, 1936, 42, 461; 1938, 46, 129) has observed that the amount of humus, irreversibly adsorbed by a clay, depends on the character of the clay, whereby mixed clay-humus micelles are formed in which majority of the clay particles possess a fairly definite orientation. According to Jung (*Bodenk. Pfl. Ernahr.*, 1943, 32, 325) the adsorption of humus materials by clays could be better expressed by a hyperbolic function than by the adsorption isotherm. The observations of Sideri (*loc. cit.*), Jung (*loc. cit.*), Myers (*Forsch. Dienst. Sonderh.*, 1941, 17, 38), Khan (*Pedology*, U.S.S.R., 1950, 673; *Doklady Akad. Nauk*, U.S.S.R., 1951, 81, 461) and others have shown that in the clay-humus combination there should be some loose chemical linkage apart from the general van der Waals type of adsorption. A few workers (Hideaki Saeki, *Jap. Assoc. Advanc. Sci.*, 1942, 16, 410; Khan, *loc. cit.*) also studied the importance of metal ions in this bonding. This aspect of the problem calls for a systematic study, which has been attempted here.

EXPERIMENTAL

Clay and humic acid sols were prepared as described previously (Sen, *loc. cit.*). The clay fractions ($< 1\mu$) from 5 different soil samples were collected in the usual way. The pH values of about 2.5% clay sol varied between 3.5 and 4.2. Humic acid was extracted from Padegaon B soil. The pH value of approximately 0.6% humic acid sol was found to be 3.5. The b.e.c. values of the pure H-clay and humic acid sol were determined by pH titration from the amount of baryta corresponding to the inflection point and reported in the earlier communication (Sen, *loc. cit.*, Table I).

The adsorption was studied in the following way. The mixtures of clay and humic acid sols in the desired proportions were kept for about a week with occasional shaking. Preliminary studies, allowing time of reaction longer than about a week, did not show any further appreciable change in the titration curves and other properties of the mixtures. Usually therefore one week's time was allowed for the interaction to proceed. Then an aliquot of each of the mixtures was taken out, and the loosely bound or adsorbed portion of humic acid was extracted by washing, repeatedly with $N/2$ Na_2CO_3 solution and centrifuged until the Na_2CO_3 extract was no longer coloured with humic acid. In the collected washings the amount of humic acid was analysed by the

method of Walkley and Black (*Soil Sci.*, 1934, **37**, 29), in which the organic matter was decomposed with chromic acid, and the residual chromic acid was titrated back with a standard Mohr salt solution using diphenylamine as indicator. Similar experiments were performed in presence of Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Al^{3+} , and Fe^{3+} ions. The amount of the respective ions added corresponds to the total exchange capacity of the clay-humic acid mixture. The cations were added in the form of chloride or sulphate, and it is likely that depending on the condition of ionic equilibrium, all the ions will not take part, if at all, in the interaction. Added in the form of oxides or hydroxides, e.g., those of Ca and Mg, the reaction is likely to be complete, as a neutralisation reaction is. In one set of experiments therefore, viz., in case of PBM clay and AGM clay, the Ca^{2+} was added in the form of hydroxide (added in amount equivalent to the b.e.c. of the mixture), and clay-humus interaction was studied in its presence just like in other cases. Then a known aliquot of each was leached several times with 200-250 c.c. of $\text{NaCl}(N)$ solution as in the determination of exchangeable Ca^{2+} . In the leachate the amount of calcium was determined by precipitation as oxalate, followed by KMnO_4 titration. The results of the above experiments are reported in Tables I and II and in Figs. 1-5.

TABLE I

Estimation of alkali-extractable humic acid from clay-humic acid mixtures.

Ions present.	Humic acid: clay.	% Humic acid combined* with different clays.				
		PBM.	AGM.	Cl.	KL.	RK.
H^{+}	1:10	30	36	20	18	12
	1:20	36	42	25	20	16
	1:40	40	50	29	25	20
	1:60	48	55	35	32	23
Ca^{2+}	1:10	38	45	28	25	18
	1:20	48	55	35	31	24
	1:40	60	68	40	37	29
	1:60	65	73	46	42	32
Mg^{2+}	1:10	44	55	35	30	22
	1:20	60	65	42	37	26.5
	1:40	70	75	47	43	33
	1:60	75	82	55	48	37
Al^{3+}	1:10	42	53	35	30	23
	1:20	56	63	40	36	27
	1:40	69	73	46	44	33
	1:60	72	82	54	48	36
Fe^{3+}	1:10	45	55	37.5	32	25
	1:20	62	66	44	38	29
	1:40	70	78	48	46	34.5
	1:60	74	83	58	50	38

N.B. For symbols vide Sen, *loc. cit.*

* Not extractable by Na_2CO_3 leaching.

TABLE II

Estimation of calcium extracted with $N\text{-NaCl}$ solution from the PBM clay-and AGM clay-crude humic acid mixtures prepared in presence of CaO .

Humic acid: clay.	CaO added.	CaO in NaCl leachate.	
	PBM clay + humic acid.		
1:10	0.0436 g.	0.0166 g.	38%
1:20	0.0343	0.0133	39
1:40	0.0414	0.0156	38
1:60	0.0340	0.0103	30
	AGM clay + humic acid.		
1:10	0.0322	0.0122	38
1:20	0.0277	0.0111	40
1:40	0.0510	0.0214	40
1:60	0.0249	0.0095	38

DISCUSSION

The results obtained definitely show that a portion of the adsorbed humic acid is not extractable by alkali treatment. This strong bonding between clay and humus is probably of a chemical

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

nature. As the proportion of humic acid decreases in the mixtures, not only is the interaction more extensive but also the intensity of interaction increases appreciably. This is shown by the gradually increasing amounts of combined humic acid with smaller proportions of it.

The interaction is also dependent on the nature of the cation present in the mixture. Mg^{2+} , Al^{3+} , and Fe^{3+} ions have nearly the same effect, viz., considerable increase in the amount of combined humic acid. H^+ ion is least effective whereas Ca^{2+} ion is intermediate. The nature of the clay mineral determines to a certain extent the intensity of interaction. In illite (CI sample) the proportion of combined humic acid is much smaller than in montmorillonite (PBM and AGM clay samples), but the order of effectiveness of the cations is the same. In kaolinite (RK clay) the intensity of interaction is the least, but here also the order of effectiveness of the cations remains the same. Between the two samples of montmorillonites, the strength of binding of humic acid is somewhat greater in AGM clay than in PBM clay. It may be noted that the crude humic acid used in these two cases was extracted from the original PBM soil (Sen, *loc. cit.*, Table I). Apparently, the higher b.e.c. of AGM clay is responsible for the stronger combination.

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

From the estimation of calcium in NaCl leachate, obtained from different clay-humic mixtures, it is seen that in every case an appreciable part of calcium added has been retained by the clay-humic acid complex. Had this calcium been present in the exchangeable position, it could have been completely leached out by the NaCl solution. Hence this suggests that part of the calcium ions is present in a non-exchangeable form in the complex, formed between humic acid and clay minerals.

FIG. 5

It may be concluded from the above observations that there must be two types of linkages between clay and humus. One is a weak bonding where perhaps the humic acid is present as a coating on the outermost surface of the clay micelle, and, as a result, it is easily extractable by alkali treatment. The other is a strong bonding corresponding to the alkali non-extractable portion where clay, humic acid, and the added cations are involved. It is likely that this clay-humus complex is formed in such a manner that the OH and COOH groups of humic acid co-ordinate with the metal ions occupying the exchangeable positions in the clay-mineral lattice.

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